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MODERN APPROACHES TO ROOT CANAL SYSTEM DISINFECTION IN THE MANAGEMENT OF APICAL PERIODONTITIS

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Abstract

Irrigation represents a critical stage in endodontic therapy aimed at decreasing microbial contamination within the root canal system. Conventional irrigating agents, although widely applied in clinical practice, are associated with several disadvantages, including cytotoxicity and limited ability to eradicate microorganisms from all anatomical regions of dentin. At present, no existing irrigation solution can be regarded as completely ideal or fully capable of achieving total canal disinfection. This article evaluates the advantages and limitations of both newly introduced and traditionally used irrigation agents and root canal decontamination techniques employed in the treatment of apical periodontitis.

Keywords: irrigants, endodontics, root canal system, sodium hypochlorite, disinfection.

Introduction

Microorganisms originating from the oral cavity are considered the principal etiological factor in endodontic infections, penetrating the root canal system and contributing to the development of periapical lesions. Successful endodontic treatment is primarily directed toward the elimination of pathogenic microorganisms and the prevention of reinfection within the canal system.

Due to the complex anatomy of root canals, including accessory canals, isthmuses, apical ramifications, and dentinal tubules, complete mechanical cleaning alone is insufficient. Therefore, chemical irrigation plays a decisive role in reducing microbial load and removing necrotic tissue remnants, smear layer components, and biofilm structures.

Sodium hypochlorite remains the most commonly used irrigating solution because of its broad antimicrobial activity and capacity to dissolve organic tissues. Nevertheless, its cytotoxic nature and potential to cause irritation when extruded beyond the apical foramen continue to be major concerns in clinical practice. Chlorhexidine has also demonstrated antimicrobial efficacy; however, unlike sodium hypochlorite, it lacks tissue-dissolving properties.

Chelating agents such as ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) are frequently applied to remove the inorganic component of the smear layer and improve canal cleanliness. Recently, growing attention has been directed toward newer irrigation systems and activation methods, including ultrasonic activation, laser-assisted irrigation, sonic devices, and negative-pressure irrigation systems. These technologies are intended to improve penetration of irrigants into anatomically inaccessible regions of the root canal system.

Despite significant progress in endodontic irrigation protocols, none of the currently available methods can ensure complete elimination of microorganisms from all areas of the canal system. For this reason, contemporary endodontics increasingly focuses on combined irrigation protocols that integrate several solutions and activation techniques to enhance treatment effectiveness while minimizing adverse effects.

The primary objective of endodontic treatment is the elimination of infected tissues and prevention of reinfection within the root canal system [3]. The complicated anatomy of root canals, insufficient mechanical debridement, and root resorption significantly complicate successful management of carious lesions [1]. Instrumentation of the canals inevitably leads to the formation of an organic and inorganic debris layer, commonly referred to as the smear layer, which contains microorganisms and byproducts of their metabolism. Considerable areas of canal

walls often remain untouched by endodontic instruments, emphasizing the necessity of chemical irrigation and disinfection to clean all portions of the canal system [2]. The success of endodontic therapy largely depends on the effectiveness of microbial elimination rather than solely on obturation quality. Therefore, proper chemo-mechanical preparation is considered more important than root canal filling itself [1–3].

At present, there is no single irrigating solution capable of fulfilling all requirements of an ideal disinfectant. Consequently, modern irrigation protocols are commonly based on the sequential use of several irrigants to achieve predictable, safe, and efficient canal disinfection.

Objectives of Root Canal Irrigation

Root canal irrigation is regarded as an essential component of endodontic treatment aimed at eliminating microorganisms from the canal system. During and after instrumentation, irrigation solutions contribute to the removal of microbes, necrotic tissues, inflammatory exudate, and dentinal debris. Irrigation also decreases friction between instruments and dentinal walls, improves cutting efficiency of files, dissolves tissue remnants, and provides cooling of both the instrument and tooth, particularly during ultrasonic activation. In addition, irrigation reduces the risk of compacting hard and soft tissue debris into the apical region and helps eliminate planktonic bacteria and biofilm formations from periapical tissues.

Characteristics of an Ideal Irrigant

An effective root canal irrigant should possess the following properties [4,8,11,12,15,18,22]:

Desired Property	Description
Antimicrobial activity	Must exhibit bactericidal and fungicidal effects
Lubrication	Should lubricate instruments during canal preparation

Desired Property	Description
Organic tissue dissolution	Ability to dissolve pulp tissue, collagen, and biofilm
Inorganic tissue dissolution	Capability to remove inorganic dentin debris
Biocompatibility	Should not damage periapical tissues
Residual antibacterial effect	Must maintain antimicrobial activity after application
Activity in organic media	Should remain effective in blood, serum, and tissue fluids
Smear layer removal	Ability to eliminate smear layer from canal walls
Low surface tension	Improved penetration into dentinal tubules
Dentinal tubule disinfection	Effective antimicrobial action within dentin
Safety	Should not irritate surrounding tissues
Structural preservation	Must not alter dentin structure or matrix metalloproteinases
Immunological safety	Should not induce cell-mediated immune responses
Absence of toxicity	No antigenic, toxic, or carcinogenic effects
Compatibility	Should not interfere with sealing materials
Practicality	Easy clinical application and low cost

Desired Property	Description
Stability	Long shelf life

Chlorhexidine digluconate (CHX) demonstrates strong antimicrobial activity, which explains its extensive application in endodontics both as an irrigating solution and as an intracanal medicament. Compared with sodium hypochlorite, chlorhexidine lacks several undesirable properties, including unpleasant odor and severe irritation of periapical tissues [23,34].

However, chlorhexidine is unable to dissolve organic tissue and therefore cannot completely replace sodium hypochlorite. Its antimicrobial mechanism involves penetration through microbial cell walls and destruction of cytoplasmic membranes in bacteria and yeast cells. At high concentrations, CHX induces coagulation of intracellular components.

One of the major advantages of chlorhexidine is its prolonged antimicrobial substantivity. After binding to hard dental tissues, it continues to exhibit antibacterial effects for an extended period. Similar to many other endodontic disinfectants, its activity depends on pH and decreases significantly in the presence of organic substances [8,10].

Most investigations evaluating CHX in endodontics have been performed using *in vitro* and *ex vivo* models, predominantly involving *Enterococcus faecalis*. Additional studies are required to establish optimal irrigation protocols for various endodontic procedures [18,27].

Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid (EDTA)

EDTA possesses the ability to dissolve inorganic components of intracanal debris and is commonly used in a 17% concentration. The combination of sodium hypochlorite and EDTA is considered one of the most effective approaches in endodontic irrigation. During mechanical preparation, abundant irrigation with sodium hypochlorite is performed, whereas EDTA is generally applied during the

final stage to remove the smear layer and inorganic debris from canal walls [13,14,21].

Antimicrobial Photodynamic Therapy (aPDT)

Antimicrobial photodynamic therapy represents a two-stage procedure involving application of a photosensitizing agent followed by light activation of sensitized tissues. This process induces toxic photochemical reactions within target cells, leading to microbial destruction.

aPDT is considered an adjunctive method to conventional root canal disinfection protocols. Continuous development of novel photosensitizers has demonstrated promising penetration into dentinal tubules and activity against biofilm-associated microorganisms, making this technique a перспективный direction in endodontic disinfection research [16,25,33].

Tetraclean®

Tetraclean® is a mixture containing doxycycline hyclate at lower concentrations than MTAD, citric acid, and detergents. This solution contributes to elimination of microorganisms and smear layer removal from infected dentinal tubules.

A final 5-minute rinse with Tetraclean® has demonstrated enhanced antimicrobial activity against *Enterococcus faecalis* biofilm. Comparative investigations evaluating 5.25% sodium hypochlorite, MTAD, and Tetraclean® revealed that sodium hypochlorite showed superior biofilm disruption and removal capabilities. Nevertheless, Tetraclean® achieved better antimicrobial performance than MTAD [1,6,29,32].

MTAD

MTAD (mixture of tetracycline isomer, acid, and detergent) and BioPure™ MTAD™ consist of doxycycline, citric acid, and a detergent component. These formulations were developed as alternatives to EDTA for smear layer removal during the final irrigation stage. MTAD exhibits antibacterial properties, good biocompatibility, and improves adhesion characteristics. Its antimicrobial effect exceeds that of chlorhexidine. MTAD is commonly used in combination with 1.3%

sodium hypochlorite to improve the effectiveness of final root canal irrigation [5,7,24,30].

Superoxidized Water

Superoxidized water is produced by electrochemical processing of saline solution through electrochemical activation. Anolyte solutions possess antimicrobial activity against bacteria, viruses, fungi, and protozoa while remaining biologically neutral toward surrounding tissues.

Experimental studies have shown that superoxidized water can serve as an alternative irrigant for smear layer removal. Investigations also demonstrated improved cleaning efficacy in the apical third of the canal system [4,26,37].

Ozonated Water

The strong antimicrobial effect of ozone (O_3) and its ability to dissolve in water have made ozonated water attractive for endodontic applications. Research indicates that although the disinfecting capability of ozonated water does not exceed sodium hypochlorite or chlorhexidine, its antimicrobial effectiveness remains relatively comparable [6,8,10,31].

Nanoparticles in Endodontic Irrigation

Nanoparticles composed of metals and metal oxides, including magnesium oxide, calcium oxide, and zinc oxide nanoparticles, possess significant antibacterial properties. Their antimicrobial action is mainly associated with electrostatic interaction between positively charged nanoparticles and negatively charged bacterial cell membranes.

Nanoparticles demonstrate antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral effects by disrupting bacterial cell walls, damaging cellular membranes, stimulating reactive oxygen species formation, and interfering with DNA replication through controlled ion release [8,13].

In irrigation solutions, nanoparticles are capable of penetrating dentinal tubules and root canal irregularities, thereby providing prolonged antimicrobial activity [28,35]. Calcium silicate nanoparticles (MCSN) have additionally shown the ability to

enhance apatite mineralization and support release of therapeutic agents within the canal system, contributing to tissue regeneration and healing [9,19,20].

The anti-biofilm properties of nanoparticles may help prevent reinfection and improve long-term treatment outcomes. Despite promising findings, further research is required to establish standardized clinical protocols and evaluate long-term toxicity and safety profiles [6,8,22,23]. Potential tooth discoloration and dentin darkening associated with some nanoparticle formulations should also be considered [18].

Nanotechnology has become an important component of contemporary endodontic therapy and restorative dentistry.

Photoactivated Disinfection

Photoactivated or light-activated disinfection represents a modern approach based on laser-activated irrigation using photon-induced photoacoustic streaming (PIPS®), photoactivated disinfection (PAD), or combinations of these techniques. This concept relies on the ability of porphyrins and photosensitizers to become activated by light and produce cytotoxic elements with therapeutic antimicrobial effects. These systems improve penetration and activation of irrigating solutions within complex endodontic spaces.

The therapeutic effect of photodynamic therapy is associated with activation of non-toxic photosensitizers localized within tissues. When exposed to light of a specific wavelength, these agents generate singlet oxygen and free radicals capable of exerting cytotoxic effects on bacterial cells [20].

Methylene blue is considered one of the most effective photosensitizers used in photodynamic therapy against oral pathogens and in endodontic disinfection procedures [21].

Toluidine blue has also demonstrated effectiveness as a photosensitizing agent. It binds to bacterial cell membranes and destroys them after laser activation. Several studies reported incomplete biofilm destruction due to insufficient penetration of the photosensitizer. However, combined use of methylene blue with red light irradiation (665 nm) resulted in a 97% reduction in bacterial viability [22].

Herbal Irrigation Solutions

Because of the cytotoxicity of many conventional irrigants and the persistence of microbial contamination within dentinal tubules, increasing attention has been directed toward herbal irrigating solutions with reduced toxicity.

Plant-based irrigants used in endodontics demonstrate a wide spectrum of biological activity, including antimicrobial effects, chelating properties, and the ability to dissolve pulp tissue remnants.

According to classifications proposed by Keil and Raut [16,32], herbal endodontic irrigants may be divided into the following categories:

Category	Function
Antimicrobial irrigants	Active against endodontic pathogens
Chelating irrigants	Remove smear layer after instrumentation
Combined-action irrigants	Possess both antimicrobial and chelating properties
Tissue-dissolving irrigants	Capable of dissolving pulp tissue remnants

Herbal irrigants with antimicrobial activity include extracts of neem (*Azadirachta indica*), triphala, propolis, *Morinda citrifolia*, aloe vera, garlic (*Allium sativum*), ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), green tea, and tea tree oil.

Additional herbal substances investigated for endodontic irrigation include tea tree oil (*Melaleuca alternifolia*), carvacrol, turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), burdock (*Arctium lappa*), babool (*Acacia nilotica*), tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*), cinnamon (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*), and miswak (*Salvadora persica*).

Chelating herbal irrigants include neem leaf extract (*Azadirachta indica*), triphala, *Morinda citrifolia*, garlic (*Allium sativum*), green tea, tea tree oil (*Melaleuca alternifolia*), tulsi leaf extract (*Ocimum sanctum*), miswak (*Salvadora persica*), grapefruit (*Citrus paradisi*), passion fruit juice, orange oil, chamomile (*Matricaria recutita*), *Terminalia chebula* seed extract, amla (*Embllica officinalis*), pomegranate

peel (*Punica granatum*), extracts of *Citrus aurantiifolia*-*Sapindus mukorossi*, *moringa oleifera*, lemongrass, and turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) [26,28,34].

Herbal extracts contain terpenoids, flavonoids, and other biologically active compounds possessing antiviral, analgesic, antimicrobial, antispasmodic, and sedative properties. When applied as irrigants, these substances disinfect the root canal system with lower toxicity compared with many conventional solutions. Their therapeutic effects additionally include immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antibacterial activity [18,25].

The principal advantages of herbal irrigants include safety, simplicity of application, cost-effectiveness, and the absence of microbial resistance development.

Conclusion

Successful root canal therapy depends on proper instrumentation, effective disinfection, and reliable obturation of the canal system. Consequently, considerable attention is currently focused on irrigation solutions with strong antimicrobial properties as an essential adjunct to mechanical preparation.

This review summarizes contemporary irrigants and root canal disinfection approaches currently available to clinicians. However, the existence of newer irrigation methods does not eliminate the importance of traditional cleaning protocols. The effectiveness of irrigation depends not only on the type of irrigant used, but also on its concentration and method of activation within the canal system. Among conventional solutions, sodium hypochlorite remains one of the most effective irrigants, and its tissue-dissolving capability has been shown to increase at concentrations of 0.5%, 2.5%, and 5.0% [12,18,31].

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